

Style for IRRN Contributors

Units of measure and styles vary from country to country. To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following style guidelines:

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg/ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the *IRRN*. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha.
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.
- Type all contributions double spaced.
- Indent first lines of each paragraph.
- Do not hyphenate words at the end of a line.

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

The origin of semidwarf genes

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The first Chinese semidwarf variety Ai-chiao-nan-te was derived from Nan-te 16. Most workers believe that it was the result of spontaneous mutation. The semidwarf gene of Ai-tsai-chan has not yet been studied in detail. As for Dee-geo-woo-gen, the records of Taiwan Fang-Chih (an 1871 book of local history) mention a rice variety called "Woo-gen" (which means brown apiculus) that was introduced from Fukien province; however, not one of the rice varieties had a name beginning with "Deo-geo," "I-deo," or "Hsia-geo" (all those prefixes mean "dwarf"), indicating that no dwarf variety was grown at that time. In 1906 both "Deo-geo-woo-gen" and "Woo-gen" appeared in the survey records of the Taipei agricultural experiment station the first clear indication of the existence of the semidwarf variety. Therefore, Dee-geo-woo-gen is generally assumed to have derived directly as a dwarf spontaneous mutant from Woo-gen. Another possibility is that a semidwarf gene caused by spontaneous mutation first appeared in some other varieties, then was transmitted to Woo-gen through a natural cross.

Interestingly, except two from mainland provinces, the semidwarfs identified so far come from Taiwan province. Semidwarfs that originated from Taiwan include Dee-geo-woo-gen, I-geo-tze, Ti-chueh-hua-lo, Ai-chueh-ching-yu, and Ai-chueh-chan. Perhaps because typhoons often strike Taiwan, lodging resistance tends to be particularly important.

The semidwarf gene may have been conserved through natural and artificial selection. Rice productivity was low in old China. For example, average annual yields in Kwang tung province were less

than 3 t/ha. The heavy-panicle-type varieties were adaptable to low-fertility conditions. Because the correlation between heavy panicles and long culms is highly significant, any semidwarf mutant that might have existed at that time would not have been selected and conserved. ■

Semidwarf gene sources of rice in China

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Until the 1950s, almost all the rice varieties grown in China were tall. Breeding for semidwarf rice varieties first started in 1956, when two farmers in Chao-yang County, Kwangtung Province, found a semidwarf plant in a plot of the tall indica variety Nan-te 16. That single semidwarf plant, which may have originated through spontaneous mutation, was selected. After thorough testing it was released as Ai-chiao-nan-te, the first semidwarf high yielding rice variety on mainland China. Its desirable features were its short culm, short and erect leaves, profuse tillering, heavy panicles, and high fertilizer response. Its average yield was 6 t/ha.

Ai-chiao-nan-te's popularity stimulated keen interest in semidwarf development. In 1957 the Kwangtung Academy of Agricultural Sciences used Ai-tsai-chan, a local semidwarf variety from Kwangsi Province, as the female parent in crosses with Kwang-chang 13 and Hui-yang-chen-chu-chao. The Academy named two progenies as the varieties Kwang-chang-ai and Chen-chu-ai in 1959 and 1962. By 1965, two semidwarfs were grown on about 160 million ha in China. They were extended throughout southern China in 1967. Their important characteristics, along with that of Dee-geo-woo-gen of Taiwan Province, are in Table 1.

Table 1. The main characteristics of Ai-chiao-nan-te, Ai-tsai-chan, and Dee-geo-woo-gen.^a China.

Designation	Origin	Maturity (days to heading)	Plant (cm)	Panicles (no./plant)	1000-grain wt (g)	Grain/panicle	Hulled grains		
							Length (mm)	Width (mm)	Length-width ratio
Ai-chiao-nan-te	Chao-yang County, Kwangtung Province	Early (73 days)	75.9	18.2	26.8	101.0	8.6	3.1	2.77
Ai-tsai-chan	Junghsien County, Kwangsi Province	Medium (101 days)	94.9	18.7	24.6	154.9	8.6	3.2	2.69
Dee-geo-woo-gen	Taiwan or Fukien Province	Medium-late (107 days)	102.0	15.3	27.1	161.8	8.3	3.2	2.59

^a Seeded on 11 March and transplanted on 11 April. Plant spacing = 40 x 20 cm.

Ai-chiao-nan-te, Ai-tsai-chan, and Dee-geo-woo-gen, have been used in the breeding of almost all modern high yielding rice varieties (Table 2). ■

Genetic analysis of dwarfism in Chinese rice

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Parnell and associates were the earliest (1922) to conduct genetic analysis on rice dwarfism. In 1925 Akemine carried out a detailed genetic analysis of three dwarf mutants — Daikoku, Ebisu, and Kodaikoku—which had been isolated from the normal variety Akage. He pointed out that tallness was dominant to dwarfness and that the three dwarf mutants resulted from the interaction between two pairs of complementary genes. That type of dwarf mutant still cannot be used in breeding programs because of complicated inheritance and undesirable traits.

Semidwarfs used as parent materials in current rice breeding programs are generally about 75 to 100 cm tall. I shall present some of my genetical research work on dwarfism. Between 1976 and 1977, three semidwarf varieties were crossed with the same tall male parent. Leng-shiu-ma (a local variety from Hunan Province).

The height of the F₂ populations of the three crosses was greater than the

Table 2. The genealogical relations among the Chinese semidwarfs.

Important varieties	Direct or indirect derivatives of
Kwang-chang-ai, Chen-chu-ai, Kwang-lu-ai 4, Nanking 11	Ai-tsai-chan
Lung-Ke 113, Kwang-Hsuan 3, Te-ku-ai 31	Ai-chiao-nan-te
Er-chiu-ai, Hung-mei-Tsao, Er-chiu-nan 1	Both Ai-chiao-nan-te and Ai-tsai-chan
TN1, Taichung Sen 2, Kaohsiung Sen 2	Dee-geo-woo-gen ^a

^a Virtually all semidwarf varieties developed at IRRI and in national rice improvement programs are also derivatives of Dee-geo-woo-gen.

mean height of their parents, but slightly less than that of the tall parent (Table 1), which shows the incomplete dominance of tallness.

The variation in plant height among F₂ populations of the various crosses was continuous, but all F₂ populations were characterized by a bimodal distribution.

Table 1. Plant height of F₁ and parents of various crosses.

Cross	Plant ht (cm)						Expression
	Female parent		F ₁ Male		parent		
	n	\bar{x}	n	\bar{x}	n	\bar{x}	
Ai-chino-nan-te/Leng-shui-ma	10	77.0	5	129.1	10	136.7	incomplete dominance
Ai-tsai-chan/Leng-shui-ma	10	68.0	8	125.6	10	136.7	"
Dee-geo-woo-gen/Leng-shui-ma	10	83.0	7	130.3	10	136.7	"

Table 2. The segregation ratio of plant height in F₂ of various crosses. Kwangchow, 1977.

Cross	Plants (no.)			Ratio (T:D)	X ²	P
	Tall form	Dwarf form	Total			
Ai-chiao-nan-te/Leng-shui-ma	210	62	272	3:1	0.75	0.50–0.30
Ai-tsai-chan/Leng-shui-ma	202	70	272	3:1	0.08	0.80–0.70
Dee-geo-woo-gen/Leng-shui-ma	210	62	272	3:1	0.75	0.50–0.30